

Vuzix M4000 User Guide

WATERLINE

A white graphic element consisting of two curved lines that sweep across the width of the page, positioned below the word "WATERLINE".

How to Assemble the Vuzix M4000

Step 1

Find your dominant eye. Make a small triangle with your hands and look at an object. Close one eye, then the other. The eye that keeps the object in view is your dominant eye.

Step 2

Slide the viewer onto the side of the glasses that matches your dominant eye.

Step 3

Move the viewer forward, backward, tilt, and rotate it until it is in the best position.

Step 4

Attach the battery to the other side of the glasses.

Step 5

Plug in the USB-C cable from the viewer to the battery. The viewer should turn on.

Step 6

Put the power cable over your head and wear the glasses like normal glasses.

How to Turn on Vuzix M4000

Step 1

Connect the USB-C cable to the viewer and the battery.

Step 2

The viewer will automatically turn on once you connect the power.

Tip: If it doesn't turn on, check that the battery is charged.

How to Adjust the Vuzix M4000 for Comfort

Step 1

Attach the viewer to either side of the glasses frame based on your dominant eye.

Step 2

Slide the viewer forward and backward to adjust it. Rotate and tilt for the best fit.

Step 3

Use ear hooks and different nose pads for a comfortable fit.

Note: Only touch the plastic parts when adjusting. Never touch the waveguide display to avoid damage.

How to Navigate the Vuzix M4000

Touchpad Navigation

- **Tap** to select items.
- **Swipe up or down** to scroll.
- **Short Press:**
 - **Front button:** Move forward.
 - **Centre button:** Go back.
 - **Back button:** Select.
- **Long Press (1 second):**
 - **Front button:** Acts like a right-click.
 - **Centre button:** Exit to home menu.
 - **Back button:** Go back one step.

How to Connect to Wi-Fi

Step 1

Create a QR code for your Wi-Fi network at www.vuzix.com/wifiQR from your phone or computer.

Step 2

Open the "Scanner" app on the Vuzix M4000.

Step 3

Centre the QR code in the viewfinder to connect to your Wi-Fi.

